

Survival of *C. longipennis* using the mass rearing technique. IIRI insectary, 1986.

Stage	Insects reared (no.)	Surviving individuals (no.)	survival (%)
Egg to 1st instar	326	307	96
1st instar to adult	40	34	85

Third instars were transferred to 20.0-cm test tubes (2.5 cm in diameter) to complete nymphal development. Newly emerged adult males and females were confined in 30- × 22- × 52.5-cm rectangular mylar cages with separate petri dishes containing 2 g of corn borer diet and moist cotton on the bottom. The moist cotton provided water and served as a suitable substrate for oviposition.

C. longipennis completed its life cycle from egg to adult in 142 to 182 d, with 80% survival (see table). The corn borer diet was suitable for rearing the insect. □

Rearing field-collected grasshoppers in the laboratory.

Effect of insecticides on rice leaffolder (LF) eggs

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We studied nine insecticides to determine their ovicidal efficacy on eggs of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) in the insectary. The experiment was in a completely randomized design with three replications, with each replication consisting of 20 eggs.

Male and female LF moths obtained from mass culture were introduced in tumbler pots containing 25-d-old rice seedlings. The tumbler pots were covered with glass chimneys 22 cm high and 7.5 cm in diameter. Oviposition was observed daily. Seedlings containing eggs were separated and planted in tumbler pots.

Insecticidal treatments were given with a hand atomizer; control pots received water spray. Hatching of larvae was recorded for each treatment.

Phosphamidon, quinalphos, and monocrotophos treatments had 100% egg mortality; fenthion followed with 96% mortality (see table). Endosulfan exhibited the least ovicidal action. □

Ovicidal action of insecticides on rice LF eggs. Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Concn. (%)	Mortality ^a (%)
Monocrotophos 36 WSC	0.05	100 a
Quinalphos 25 EC	0.05	100 a
Phosphamidon 85 WSC	0.045	100 a
Fenthion 100 EC	0.01	96 a
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	0.04	54 b
Malathion 50 EC	0.1	46 b
Dichlorvos 100 EC	0.02	42 b
Carbaryl 50 WP	0.1	42 b
Endosulfan 35 EC	0.07	21 c
No insecticide (control)	Water spray	11 d

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT.

Leaffolder (LF) resurgence and species composition in Pattambi, Kerala

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In field trials 1983-85 at Pattambi, LF damage was higher in maximum protection treatments (MPT) (see figure). In both the first crop (May-Aug) and second crop (Sep-Feb), MPT plots receiving carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT) recorded higher LF damage (90% in the first crop, 55% in the second) than the no-insecticide plot.

Triazophos effectively controlled LF. Carbosulfan was no different from no insecticide. With synthetic pyrethroid, damage was 10-25%.

To corroborate these findings, we conducted an observational trial in 90-m² plots using EC (emulsifiable